

Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein Distributions Based on Kinematics

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Traditionally in textbooks, the Fermi-Dirac (FD) and Bose-Einstein (BE) equilibrium distributions are derived either by using a factorial counting approach (used by Planck in the early 1900s) or through the grand canonical partition function. There is also interest in creating entropy functions which may yield all possible distributions when maximized subject to constraints, usually an energy constraint. In this note, we argue that like the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution case which may be obtained solely through kinematics $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ and conservation of energy in a scattering reaction, so too the FD and BE distributions may be obtained. In addition, we try to compare this approach with the grand canonical partition function calculation.

Kinematics

It seems that in a classical gas or a gas of fermions and bosons, there are two body collisions which conserve energy. Thus, one solution for equilibrium is to have the probability for each possible type of reaction to occur match that of its time reversed reaction. In such a way, the number of particles in each state should remain the same, thus yielding a static or equilibrium scenario. For the MB case, one is led to an “and” probability scenario, namely for $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$:

$$f(e_1) f(e_2) = f(e_3) f(e_4) \quad ((1))$$

Taking the ln of ((1)) and equating the resulting conservation equation with energy yields:

$$\ln(f(e_i)) = -1/T e_i \quad \text{or} \quad f(e_i) = C \exp(-1/T e_i) \quad \text{the MB distribution} \quad ((2))$$

((2)) also happens to maximize Shannon’s entropy subject to an energy constraint because the kinematics impose no extra constraints.

Alternatively, one may replace ((2)) with $\ln(f(e_i)) = -1/T (e_i - u)$ where u is the chemical potential. The fugacity then takes the place of the normalization constant for $N=1$.

The case of fermions and bosons is not so simple because there are physical constraints in the picture it seems which change ((1)). For fermions, e_1 cannot scatter into e_3 if e_3 is occupied and the same restriction holds for e_2 as well as similar restrictions for the time reversed reaction. The probability for e_3 to be occupied seems to be proportional to $f(e_3)$ so $1-f(e_3)$ is the probability that e_3 is empty. Thus, $f(e_1)$ should be replaced with $f(e_1)[1-f(e_3)]$. Similar arguments hold e_2 and e_4 . Thus, ((1)) seems to be replaced with:

$$f(e_1) [1-f(e_3)] f(e_2) [1 - f(e_4)] = f(e_3) [1-f(e_1)] f(e_4) [1-f(e_2)] \quad ((3))$$

Rearranging, taking ln and equating to e_i for conservation of energy yields:

$$\ln [f(e_i) / (1-f(e_i))] = -1/T (e_i-u) \quad ((4))$$

Solving yields: $f(e_i) = 1 / [1+ \exp(-1/T (e_i-u))] \quad ((5))$ FD distribution.

Here T is temperature and u the chemical potential. (As mentioned above $\exp(-1/T(e-u))$ is a normalized MB function if $N=1$, thus fugacity serves the role of a normalization constant for the MB case.) Thus, the FD distribution may be obtained strictly from kinematics and conservation of energy with no need for entropy maximization or the counting of states.

A similar approach seems to hold for the BE case. Feynman (1) has shown that if there are n bosons in a state, the probability to add an additional one is enhanced by $n+1$. (Often, this idea is applied to photons). Thus, in the reaction $e_1+e_2 = e_3 + e_4$, if there are $f(e_3)$ particles in e_3 the probability of e_1 converting to e_3 seems to be $f(e_1) (1+ f(e_3))$. Thus for bosons:

$$f(e_1) [1+f(e_3)] f(e_2) [1+f(e_4)] = f(e_3) [1+f(e_1)] f(e_4) [1+ f(e_2)] \quad ((6))$$

Taking the ln, and equating to energy (or $-1/T(e_i-u)$) for energy conservation yields:

$$\ln [f(e_i) / (1+ f(e_i))] = -1/T (e_i-u) \quad ((7)) \quad \text{which yields:}$$

$$f(e_i) = 1 / [1-\exp(-1/T (e_i-u))] \quad \text{the BE distribution} \quad ((7))$$

Thus, kinematics and conservation of energy seem to be all that is needed to derive the FD and BE distributions. It also should be noted that in both cases, one obtains the following forms:

$$\ln(k(f(e_i))) = -1/T (e_i-u) \quad ((8)) \quad \text{For the FD case: } k= f(e_i)/ [1-f(e_i)] \quad \text{and for BE } k= f(e_i)/ [1+f(e_i)]$$

Considering ((8)), $\ln(k(f(e_i))) = \text{so } \ln(k)$ is the inverse function of f.

One may verify this for the FD and BE cases.

Thus, kinematics leads to the idea of function-inverse function pairs. These ideas may be extended to Tsallis and Kaniadakis statistics. Kaniadakis in (2) derives a Kramers equation and introduces kinematics such as those used above. For example, he introduces a function $G(f(e_1),f(e_3))$ to describe $f(e_1)$ scattering into $f(e_3)$. He then suggests that:

$$G(f(e_1), f(e_3)) / G(f(e_3), f(e_1)) = k(f(e_1)) / k(f(e_3)) \quad ((8))$$

He goes on to develop a form for entropy and obtains the equilibrium distribution by taking $d/ds(f) - \beta d/df(e - f)$ instead of directly using balance equations like ((3)) and ((6)) which appear at earlier stages within his equations (see (3)). It seems, however, that he wishes to obtain an expression for entropy even in non-equilibrium cases.

Grand Canonical Partition Function

Textbooks (4) often use the grand canonical partition function, or a factorial counting approach to obtain the FD and BE distributions. This begs the question: How is the kinematical approach used above linked to the grand canonical distribution?

The grand canonical approach assumes an average macrostate energy E and an average macrostate number of particles N . It also assumes an MB or Shannon's maximum entropy distribution of $\exp(-1/T(E_i - uN_i))$ as a weight for each macrostate. Physical constraints associated with fermions or bosons are then introduced as different macrostates. For example, for fermions, one macrostate may include 0 fermions in state e_i while another macrostate would include one fermion. The approach then proceeds to consider the microstates comprising each macrostate and the result is that these do not follow the MB or maximum Shannon entropy result. For example:

$N_i = \sum n_i$ where n_i is the number of particles in the microstate state (single particle state) with energy e_i .

$E_i = \sum n_i e_i$

One may immediately ask how this differs from the MB case? It seems that by considering different macrostates, one is inserting the restrictions or constraints involved with fermions and bosons. For example, there may be one fermion or zero fermions (ignoring spin) in a state e_i . If the fermion is there, it contributes to the overall $\exp(-1/T(E_i - uN_i))$ a factor $\exp(-1/T(e_i - u))$ i.e. the MB probability, but if it is absent, it contributes a factor 1. Thus, in the MB case, one has $f(e_i)$, but in the FD case $1 + f(e_i)$. This is different physics it seems, but ultimately leads to a kind of renormalization.

For the FD case, one finally takes \ln of the grand canonical partition function and then d/du where u is the chemical potential. This leads to the FD distribution. It is often argued that in the limit of high T (temperature), the FD distribution becomes the MB distribution, but what seems to happen is that in this limit, one simply removes the fermion restriction. Thus, the FD distribution seems to have the appearance of a renormalization of the MB distribution i.e.

$$FD \ n = \exp(-1/T(e-u)) / [1 + \exp(-1/T(e-u))]$$

The denominator represents the "physics" of the fermion restriction. Thus, to take a high temperature limit seems to indicate that the fermion restriction "disappears" or almost

disappears if the occupations of e_i states becomes very small i.e. the value of the MB $f(e_i)$ is small. (It seems, however, that there are energies e_i near the value of T for which the $f(e_i)$ are not small, thus one seems to be considering the tail.)

For the boson case things are different. For the MB case, one has $f(e_i)$ as the probability for a particle to be in the state e_i and one does not go further. For bosons, one seems to say that there may be 0 bosons 1 boson, or 2 or 3 etc in the state so one has an “or” probability case:

$1 + f(e_i) + f(e_i)*f(e_i) + f(e_i)*f(e_i)*f(e_i) + \dots$ I.e. a geometric series with the possibility of 0 particles in state e_i . Note: $f(e_i) < 1$ so the successive terms drop off rapidly. Even if one begins with $f(e_i) = .9$, this number will drop substantially after a few terms. Thus, in the boson case, $f(e_i)$ is replaced with $1 / [1 - f(e_i)]$ with the term:

$$[1 - f(e_i)]^N = 1 \text{ from the geometric series sum}$$

Thus, taking \ln of the partition function and d/du leads to the BE distribution.

Thus, it seems the grand canonical partition function really allows one to average over the physical restrictions introduced by fermions and bosons. One begins with the Shannon’s maximum entropy distribution or MB distribution $f(e_i) = \exp(-1/T(e_i - u))$ and then involves it in further restrictions (i.e. the presence or absence of a particle for FD) or the presence of one or more particles in the same state e_i for bosons.

This then leads to the same result as the kinematical-conservation of energy approach for two particle scattering. One may ask how the grand canonical partition function approach is related to two particle scattering. Consider the fermion case. In the kinematical approach one has for the MB case: $f(e_1)$ for e_1 going to e_3 , but for the fermion case, e_3 may be occupied and so e_1 cannot scatter into it. Thus, there are two scenarios: A) e_1 scatters into e_3 or B) it doesn’t. In the kinematical approach, one simply writes $f(e_1)[1 - f(e_3)]$, but in the grand canonical partition function, one considers the two scenarios as part of two different macrostates, one with e_3 occupied and one with it empty.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that by considering the kinematics of two body elastic scattering one may obtain the equilibrium distribution for the MB, FD and BE cases. Following Kaniadakis (2), we also argue that conservation of energy combined with kinematics for even more general cases leads to: $\ln(k f(e_i)) = -1/T (e_i - u)$ where k is a function obtained from the kinematics. Thus, $\ln(k)$ and $f(e_i)$ are inverse functions, so $f(e_i)$ depends on k . One does not need any notion of entropy or its maximization, state counting or partition functions in order to obtain such distributions it seems.

References

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